

205. Two unusual microlens alerts

MY LAST three essays have been on the Gaia photometric alerts system (Hodgkin et al., 2021). In essay 202, I described the system and some of its discoveries. In essay 203 I looked at Gaia’s third exoplanet, the microlens system Gaia22dkvLb. Essay 204 was on the eclipsing AM CVn-type cataclysmic variable Gaia14aae.

Here, I will look at two other interesting microlens systems discovered by means of the science alerts pipeline: Gaia19dke, a long-duration event with multiple peaks, and Gaia19bld, in which arc-like sub-images have been spatially resolved. . . and observed rotating.

TENS OF THOUSANDS of microlensing events have been discovered in the past 30 years, most by the dedicated search teams OGLE, MOA and KMT, with a growing number found by large-scale photometric transient surveys such as ASAS-SN, Pan-STARRS and ZTF.

I gave an introduction to Gaia’s microlensing events in essay 84. Of course, Gaia provides only relatively sparse and irregular sampling: the average number of observations per source over the 34-month interval of DR3 (2014–2017) is about 40, with only 20 or so in the bulge region, although up to some 100 at intermediate ecliptic latitudes. But it has all-sky coverage, high photometric accuracy, and spans a wide range of magnitudes. Accompanying Data Release 3, Wyrzykowski et al. (2023) reported 363 Gaia discoveries, 90% of them unique.

Many complexities enter the characterisation and modelling of microlensing events (e.g. Reksini & Batista, 2024). The main parameters of relevance for this essay are the angular ‘Einstein radius’ of the event, $\theta_E \propto M_L^{1/2}$, and the associated linear Einstein radius, $R_E = \theta_E D_L$, where M_L and D_L are the lens mass and distance.

The total magnification of an event varies with time due to the relative transverse motion between source, lens, and observer. For a relative source–lens transverse velocity, v_\perp , a typical event time scale is then given by the Einstein radius crossing time, $t_E = R_E / v_\perp$.

For a bulge source (at 8 kpc), and a $1 M_\odot$ lens half way to the source, this ‘Einstein time’ is around 35 d. Longer duration events are either more massive, and/or with a small relative velocity between source and lens.

THE LONGEST recorded event, OGLE-1999-BUL-32 (MACHO-99-BLG-22), had $t_E = 640$ d (Mao et al., 2002). Long-duration events found in the Gaia alerts include Gaia18cbf, $t_E = 491$ d (Kruszyńska et al., 2022), and Gaia19dke, $t_E = 159$ d (Maskoliūnas et al., 2023).

The top panel below shows the G-band photometry for Gaia19dke over five years (other photometry, including ZTF, is shown below). Modelling by Maskoliūnas et al. (2023) shows that the event is due only to a single unresolved lens, with mass $M_L = 0.50 M_\odot$ at distance $D_L = 3.1$ kpc (source distance $D_S = 4.9$ kpc). The prominent *multiple* peaks might therefore seem surprising.

Recall that long events arise from large M_L and/or small v_\perp . In the latter case, good source–lens alignment can extend over many months. As first described by Smith et al. (2002), multiple peaks can then result from small variations in this general alignment as the Earth (and Gaia) move in their annual orbit around the Sun.

Incidentally, the time scale of lensing events tends to increase with Galactic longitude (Mróz et al., 2019), due to the fact that, away from the bulge, both lens and source are generally located in the disk, and are often therefore moving with similar transverse velocities.

Maskoliūnas et al. (2023) used the presence of this annual parallax, due to the Earth’s motion, to infer the lens mass. This, combined with their blending analysis, suggests that the dark lens is an isolated white dwarf. Direct verification of these parameters will be possible with the epoch astrometry expected with Data Release 4.

Maskoliūnas et al. (2023)

ANOTHER OF Gaia’s microlensing alerts discoveries is **Gaia19bld**. This was announced on 2019-04-18, as it brightened, at $G = 14.44$ mag (compared with the historic $G = 14.82 \pm 0.05$ mag). The Gaia light curve is well defined, with nearly 200 observations between 2014–23, and reaching a peak of $G = 10.5$ mag, three months after the alert was issued. Photometry from the Las Cumbres Observatory (LCO) established it as a microlens event, with LCO–NRES spectroscopy showing features consistent with a K3 supergiant (Rybicki et al., 2019).

The interest of Gaia19bld (with $t_E \sim 107$ d) is that, for the first time, the rotating arc-like sub-images have been resolved using the ESO VLT–PIONIER interferometer.

I SHOULD START with a brief summary of the extensive analysis by Rybicki et al. (2022), which provides the context. They assembled a large collection of photometric measurements of the ongoing event, including by the Spitzer space telescope. Together these defined the entire high-magnification event (left image), as well as resolving the event peak (right image). The best-fit model is found for a point lens, but with a finite source size.

The microlens parallax could be inferred from the difference in light-curve profile seen from Earth and from Spitzer (which, in its Earth-trailing orbit, was at a distance of about 1 au). Their derived parameters gave a (dark/unseen) lens mass, $M_L = 1.13M_\odot$, at a distance $D_L = 5.52$ kpc. Similar results were found from the spectroscopic follow-up by Bachelet et al. (2022).

THE INDIVIDUAL images of the source in microlensing events are unresolved by monolithic ground-based telescopes, even the largest, and the changing brightness (and position) of an event is simply from the superposed (and changing) flux of the individual images. For example, Gaia19dke is unresolved even at the 20 milli-arcsec inner working angle of Gemini North 8-m with the Alopeke speckle imager (Maskoliūnas et al., 2023).

Measuring the image separation would provide another route for determining the lens mass. And note that these (normally unresolved) sub-images rotate on the sky with time as the event alignment changes.

Prospects for resolving the individual images, or at least measuring their angular separation, has improved with the development of long-baseline interferometry (Delplancke et al., 2001; Dalal & Lane, 2003; Rattenbury & Mao, 2006; Cassan & Ranc, 2016; Cassan, 2023).

Cassan et al. (2022)

THE FIRST RESOLVED IMAGING of a microlensing event used the VLTI–GRAVITY interferometer for the ASAS-alerted non-bulge system TCP J0507+2447 (Dong et al., 2019). While not providing a ‘picture’ as such, the instantaneous (single-epoch) separation of the individual lensed images of the background source was determined from the interferometric ‘closure phase’. They derived an image separation 3.78 ± 0.05 mas, and hence the Einstein radius $\theta_E = 1.87 \pm 0.03$ mas.

More strikingly, Cassan et al. (2022) used the VLTI–PIONIER interferometer (Le Bouquin et al., 2011) to observe Gaia19bld. They used the four ESO 1.8-m Auxiliary Telescopes, with baselines up to 128 m, on three dates in July 2019 (just two are shown above). The source was split into two images on either side of the lens, and the arc-like images are seen to be rotating around the lens.

From the image separation, they derived the angular Einstein radius $\theta_E = 0.0818 \pm 0.0020$ mas, in agreement with the Earth–Spitzer (microlens parallax) value $\theta_E = 0.0823 \pm 0.0018$ mas by Rybicki et al. (2022), and subsequent spectroscopic observations by Bachelet et al. (2022). These spectroscopic observations also characterised the source as a red giant of radius $40 \pm 10R_\odot$.

Combining θ_E and the microlens parallax ϖ_E yields the microlens mass, $M_L = 1.147 \pm 0.029M_\odot$, which they were able to measure to an unprecedented accuracy compared with other microlensing events. The model fits also provide distance estimates to both the source, $D_S = 8.4 \pm 1.5$ kpc, and the lens, $D_L = 5.5 \pm 0.6$ kpc.

LET ME SUMMARISE. The Gaia alerts pipeline is able to identify microlens systems outside the bulge region, some with relatively nearby (1–2 kpc) sources, and of unusually long duration. In favourable circumstances, the Gaia light curve can contribute to determining the microlens parallax, ϖ_E , while progress in ground-based interferometry is allowing the direct determination of the Einstein radius θ_E , rather than waiting several years to resolve the source–lens separation as the alignment degrades (e.g. Bennett et al., 2006).

In many of these events observed by Gaia, the forthcoming availability of the intermediate astrometry with Data Release 4 (essay 11) will be another important milestone in event classification.